

LEADERSHIP STYLES

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Leadership is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon influenced by various factors. The concept is being influenced by the leadership styles which leads to appropriate, under or over leading and the readiness of the followers to receive the direction (Sethuraman & Suresh, 2014). According to Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy, 2014, Leadership is a social influence process in which the leader seeks the voluntary participation of subordinates in an effort to reach organization goals. A leader can be defined as a person who delegates or influencing others to act so as to carry out specified objectives. Udin (2024) stated that leadership styles play a critical role in influencing sustainable performance and shaping organizational dynamics. A nuanced understanding of different leadership styles may have distinct impacts on the long-term success of performance to ensure organizational sustainability. They are essential for guiding organizations toward achieving their goals, fostering innovation, and maintaining employee satisfaction.

Leadership is one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance. It is assumed that the kind of leadership style employed in an organization has an impact on its overall performance (Akpap, Jengre and Mogre, 2019). Today's organizations need effective leaders who understand the complexities of the rapidly changing global environment. If the task is highly structured and the leader has good relationship with the employees, effectiveness will be high on the part of the employees.

Leadership styles play an important role especially in shaping organizational culture, employee behavior, and overall performance. It can be defined as a foundational concept in organizational behavior and management. It represents the approach a leader takes in guiding, motivating, and managing teams to achieve organizational goals. The choice of a leadership style has a direct impact on organizational culture, employee morale, and overall productivity.

There are different types of leadership styles namely: Laissez-faire, Transformational, Autocracy, Transactional leadership, Bureaucratic, Democratic leadership, Servant, Participative, Visionary, Coaching leadership, Democracy, Authoritarian leadership, Situational Leadership, Authoritative leadership, Coaching, Transactional, Charismatic leadership, Strategic leadership, Delegative leadership, Leadership styles, Pacesetter leadership, Coach-style, Identity leadership style, and Strategic style. In this article, we will be focusing on a few of the above styles.

- 1. Laissez-Faire Leadership:** This style of leadership allows employees significant autonomy as the name suggests, providing minimal guidance and supervision. Leaders delegate authority and decision-making, employees are expected to be self-motivated and accountable, and there is minimal interference from leadership which encourages creativity and innovation in skilled teams.
- 2. Transformational Leadership:** Transformational leadership has been a cornerstone in leadership studies, emphasizing the leader's ability to inspire and motivate followers toward achieving collective goals (Bass, 1985). Transformational leaders are usually visionaries, they like to foster an environment of growth, collaboration, and innovation. They are often characterized by their ability to inspire, intellectually stimulate, and show concern for their team members individual needs. They promote continuous learning, improvement and innovation, strong emotional intelligence. Overall, transformational leadership has been shown to significantly enhance employee motivation, and overall satisfaction, which could contribute positively to organizational performance.
- 3. Autocratic Leadership:** Autocratic leadership is a directive style where the leader makes decisions independently and exercises high levels of control over the team. While often seen as outdated, it can be useful in specific scenarios where quick decision-making is essential, or in crises where a strong, authoritative presence is needed. Autocratic leadership can be suitable in environments where quick decision-making is critical, but it may stifle creativity and reduce employee satisfaction over time.
- 4. Transactional Leadership:** Transactional leadership, also known as managerial leadership, is a leadership style where leaders rely on rewards and punishments to achieve optimal job performance from their subordinates. It is a style that is focused on structured processes and rewards. Leaders focus on achieving short-term goals and performing tasks correctly and to specifications by relying on a system of rewards and punishments to manage performance and ensure that tasks are completed as per established standards. This style is often considered more pragmatic and is commonly used in organizations that prioritize efficiency and stability. Although Transactional leadership can be effective in situations where clear rules and guidelines are necessary, it may limit organizational adaptability and employee engagement over the long term.

5. Democratic Leadership: This style of leadership is also known as the participative leadership, it involves team members in decision-making processes. Democracy in this style involves being a leader of the people by the people and for the people. Leaders following this style value collaboration and encourage open communication, making it a popular choice in organizations that prioritize inclusivity and employee involvement. Both leaders and employees in organisations are involved in decision-making. Democratic leadership can significantly boost employee morale and commitment, making it highly effective in environments that value creativity and team involvement.

In conclusion, leadership style plays a crucial role in shaping organizational culture, influencing employee engagement, and driving overall performance. Each leadership style has distinct effects on organizational culture but it is important to note that the effectiveness of each style depends largely on the organization's needs, goals, and culture. Leaders often blend styles to create a flexible approach that aligns with changing organizational demands to be more effective. By understanding and applying diverse leadership styles effectively, leaders can create resilient, adaptive, and high-performing organizations.

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